

Microtubule-associated protein 6 (MAP6) or stable tubule-only polypeptide (STOP or STOP protein) : Machine learning discoveries of 2nd order synergy in Meningiomas

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Abstract

Background : MAP6 / STOP gene encodes a microtubule-associated protein (MAP) which is calmodulin (Ca²⁺ calcium-modulated protein) binding, and calmodulin-regulated protein that is involved in microtubule (polymers of tubulin that are a part of the cytoskeleton and provide structure and shape to eukaryotic cells) stabilization. They have been implicated in Parkinson's disease, schizophrenia, skeletal muscle organization, autism and osteosarcoma. However, its role in meningiomas has not yet been determined. Meningiomas are the most common intracranial primary neoplasm in adults. Patel et al. [1] analyzed 160 tumors from all 3 World Health Organization (WHO) grades (I through III) using clinical, gene expression, and sequencing data and using unsupervised clustering analysis identified 3 molecular types (A, B, and C) that reliably predicted recurrence. Further, these groups did not directly correlate with the WHO grading system, which classifies more than half of the tumors in the most aggressive molecular type as benign. **Issue** : Increasing evidence point to the fact that meningioma classification and grading, that is based on histopathology does not always accurately predict tumor aggressiveness and recurrence behaviour and knowledge of the underlying biology of the treatment resistant meningiomas and the impact of genetic alterations in these tumors, is lacking. At the current stage more genomic studies are required to unravel the role of other genes and their interactions with other genetic factors. **Resolution** : In a recently published work Sinha [2], a frame work of a search engine was developed which can rank combinations of factors (genes/proteins) in a signaling pathway. Adapting this search engine to the Meningioma dataset, i present here 2nd order combinations of MAP6, some of which have been known to exist via wet lab experiments, but many are yet to be tested. The reveals combinations might help oncologists/biologists test possible hypotheses that might be the causing factors in meningioma. Further, in my limited grasp, if proven true, the combinations revealed by the search engine might pave way for development of gene based therapies aimed

*ML dicoveries of MAP6 synergy in Meningiomas

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at resolving pathological issues related to meningiomas.

Keywords: MAP6, Meningioma, Sensitivity analysis, Machine learning.

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1. Introduction

1.1. Meningioma

Meningiomas are the most common intracranial primary neoplasm in adults. They arise from the arachnoid cap cells. These arachnoid cap cells are specialized cells that make up the arachnoid mater (one of the three protective membranes covering the brain and spinal cord). The arachnoid mater is one of the three meninges. The other two that constitute the meninges are dura mater and pia mater.

1.1.1. World Health Organization (WHO) classification

The meningiomas are classified into three grades by WHO under the Central Nervous System tumours, namely, Grade I (benign), Grade II (atypical) and Grade III (anaplastic/malignant), based on histopathology or subtype (Louis et al. [3]). As of 2021, there

exists 12 histopathological meningioma subtypes according to a mini-review by Torp et al. [4]. They are meningothelial, fibrous, transitional, psammomatous, angiomatous, microcystic, secretory, lymphoplasmacyte-rich, atypical, chordoid, clear cell and anaplastic (malignant) meningioma.

1.1.2. Historical perspective

Czarnetzki et al. [5] investigated a skull that was excavated at Steinheim/Murr (Baden-Württemberg, Germany) and consisted of a well preserved plagiocephalic cranium, with most of the facial skeleton intact. Their results of stratigraphical dating suggested the fossil specimen of *Homo steinheimensis*, was about 3,65,000 years old. In the fossile, they found that several features of the inner cranial table were consistent with a diagnosis of meningioma.

As documented in Okonkwo and Laws Jr [6], in 1614, Felix Plater, Professor of Medicine, issued a case report from the University of Basel on Caspar Bonecurtius, a noble knight stating -

began to lose his mind gradually over a two year period, to such an extent that finally he was completely stupefied and did nothing rationally. He had no desire for food and ate only when forcibly fed. ... Finally after matters had gone on thus for six months, he died.

Further, the autopsy report of Plater stated the following -

a round fleshy tumor, like an acorn. It was hard and full of holes and was as large as a medium-sized apple. It was covered with its own membrane and was entwined with veins. However, it was free of all connections with the matter of the brain, so much so that when it was removed by hand, it left behind a remarkable cavity.

This was the first case in the history that documented a patient with a lesion that was most compatible with a meningioma.

Next, in a contribution by Italian scientists, Paterniti [7] documents the first contribution of Andrea Vacca' Berlinghieri in 1813 in a manuscript *Trattato di Chirurgia Pratica*, which was never published. Its discovery was made accidentally by David Giordano, who referred in detail in an article on surgeon of Pisa in *La chirurgia di Andrea Vacca' Berlinghieri*. *Riv Storia Sci MedNat*. 1927: XVIII (3-4): 75-106. The unpublished manuscript of 488 pages describes that Vacca Berlinhieri proposed and performed a most bold radical operation. After a craniectomy with five or six burr holes on the outskirts of the fungus, the tumor was removed together the dura mater from which it originated, tying the cut vessels.

In 1847, Zanobi Pecchioli, Professor of Clinical Surgery and Operative Medicine at Modena and then at Siena University, published an account of surgeries performed during 16 years, from 1832 to 1847 (16 of the 1524 reported operations involved trephining of the skull). In one of these interventions, he carried out on July 29 1835, in Siena, for the resection of a meningioma, a defined fungus of the duramater. The case was not referred in the literature by Pecchioli but was described by in Pecchioli [8]. Finally, Cushing [9] coined the modern term of "meningioma".

Figure 1: A schematic diagram of different pathways in different meningiomas, as provided by Szulzewsky et al. [12] under CC-BY Attribution 4.0 International license (<https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>)

1.1.3. Pathophysiology

Meningiomas arise from arachnoidal cap cells, most of which are near the vicinity of the venous sinuses, and this is the site of greatest prevalence for meningioma formation. The dural venous sinuses (also called dural/cerebral/cranial sinuses) are venous sinuses (channels) found between the periosteal and meningeal layers of dura mater in the brain. They receive blood from the cerebral veins, and cerebrospinal fluid (CSF) from the subarachnoid space via arachnoid granulations. They mainly empty into the internal jugular vein. Cranial venous sinuses communicate with veins outside the skull through emissary veins. These communications help to keep the pressure of blood in the sinuses constant. (contributors [10] and Pamir et al. [11]) A schematic diagram for different pathways in different meningiomas has been provided in figure 1.

1.2. Microtubule-associated protein 6 (MAP6) or stable tubule-only polypeptide (STOP or STOP protein)

MAP6 or STOP protein in humans is encoded by the MAP6 gene which is a microtubule-associated protein (MAP). This is a calmodulin binding, and calmodulin-regulated protein that is involved in microtubule stabilization. Calmodulin (CaM) (an abbreviation for calcium(Ca^{2+})-modulated protein) is a Ca^{2+} -binding messenger protein expressed in all eukaryotic cells. MAPs interact with the microtubules of the cellular cytoskeleton. Microtubules are polymers of tubulin that form part of the cytoskeleton and pro-

vide structure and shape to eukaryotic cells. Tubulin refers either to the tubulin protein superfamily of globular proteins, or a member protein of that superfamily. The cytoskeleton is a complex-dynamic network of interlinking protein filaments present in the cytoplasm of all cells and in eukaryotes, it extends from the cell nucleus to the cell membrane. It is composed of : microfilaments, intermediate filaments, and microtubules, which are capable of rapid growth and or disassembly, depending on the cell's requirements.

Margolis et al. [13] purified and assayed the cold-stable microtubules and STOP protein.

Microtubules, ordinarily cold-labile structures, are made entirely resistant to cold temperature by the presence of substoichiometric amounts of STOP (stable tubule only polypeptide), a microtubule-associated protein. Pirollet et al. [14] produced a monoclonal antibody which recognized a 145-kDa protein previously implicated in STOP activity in rat brain extracts. They concluded that the 145-kDa protein accounts for all measurable STOP activity in rat neuronal extracts. For this, they developed an assay of microtubule cold stability and showed STOP activity was most abundant in neuronal tissue, while being detectable in all tissues tested, with the exception of heart muscle. In all tissues that they examined, STOP activity washes out as a single peak from heparin affinity columns, and in common with brain STOP, all activity is Ca^{2+} -calmodulin sensitive. Finally, they state that a similar, but not identical, analogue of brain STOP thus appears to be widespread in mammalian tissues.

Nerve cells contain abundant subpopulations of cold-stable microtubules. After previously isolating a calmodulin-regulated brain protein, STOP, which reconstitutes microtubule cold stability when added to cold-labile microtubules in vitro, Bosc et al. [15] cloned cDNA encoding STOP to find that it is a 100.5-kDa protein with no homology to known proteins. They further observed that the primary structure of STOP included two distinct domains of repeated motifs, with the central region of STOP containing 5 tandem repeats of 46 amino acids; its C terminus containing 28 imperfect repeats of an 11-amino acid motif and a SH3-binding motif close to its N terminus. Observation showed that in vitro translated STOP bound to both microtubules and Ca^{2+} -calmodulin. On expressing STOP cDNA in cells that lacked cold-stable microtubules, they observed that STOP associated with microtubules at 37 degrees C, and stabilized microtubule networks, thus inducing cold stability, nocodazole resistance, and tubulin dephosphorylation on microtubules in transfected cells. Based on this, they concluded that STOP must play an important role in the generation of microtubule cold stability and in the control of microtubule dynamics in brain.

Denarier et al. [16] isolated and characterized genomic clones spanning 67 kb and encompassing the mouse STOP gene (Mtap6). These clones derived from a single gene mapping to the E2-F1 region of mouse chromosome 7 and the protein encoded by the mouse STOP gene (Mtap6) was composed of 906 amino acids and presented a 91% identity with the rat brain STOP. It was observed that the 5' flanking region of the gene lacked a TATA box or an initiator element at usual position.

1.3. MAP6 role in different diseases

Aberrant glycosylation of proteins has major implications for human diseases. By injection of 1-methyl-4-phenyl-1,2,3,6-tetrahydropyridine (MPTP) in a mouse model of **Parkinson's disease** (PD), Ma et al. [17] tried to determine whether protein glycosylation contributed to the pathogenesis of PD. They verified the induction of PD-like features via assessing motor impairment and confirming reductions in biological markers, including dopamine, 5-hydroxytryptamine and tyrosine hydroxylase, and also the aggregation of α -synuclein. They detected altered glycosylation using biotinylated agaricus bisporus lectin, which specifically bound exposed Gal-(β -1,3)-GalNAc linked to glycoproteins. Further, they observed that enhanced glycosylation of MAP6 in PD mice as compared to healthy controls while confirming that MAP6 was glycosylated with Gal-(β -1,3)-GalNAc oligosaccharides, which in turn altered the distribution and structure of MAP6 complexes within neurons. Theirs, was the first study to explain MAP6 as a glycoprotein containing Gal-(β -1,3)-GalNAc oligosaccharides and to show that hyperglycosylation of MAP6 was strongly associated with the pathogenesis of PD.

Previous works have indicated an important role of the microtubule-associated protein STOP in the induction of microtubule cold stability, which is thought to be essential for neuronal development, maintenance, and function. Andrieux et al. [18] developed STOP null mice, devoid of cold-stable microtubules. They observed that STOP^{-/-} mice had no detectable defects in brain anatomy but showed synaptic defects, with depleted synaptic vesicle pools and impaired synaptic plasticity, associated with severe behavioral disorders. Further, a survey of the effects of psychotropic drugs on STOP^{-/-} mice behavior showed specific effects of long-term administration of neuroleptics in alleviating these disorders. Their study showed that STOP was responsible for the stability properties of neuronal microtubules and important for synaptic plasticity, while STOP^{-/-} mice might yield a pertinent model for study of neuroleptics in illnesses such as **schizophrenia**, currently thought to result from synaptic defects.

The MAP6 Knockout (KO) mouse is a microtubule-deficient model of **schizophrenia** that exhibits severe behavioral disorders that are associated with synaptic plasticity anomalies. These defects are alleviated by neuroleptics (gold standard molecules for the treatment of schizophrenia), as well as by Epophilone D (Epo D; a microtubule-stabilizing molecule). Daoust et al. [19] injected MnCl₂ in the primary somatosensory cortex, to compare the neuronal transport between MAP6 KO and wild-type mice and to measure the effect of Epo D treatment on neuronal transport in KO mice. Using manganese-enhanced magnetic resonance imaging (MEMRI), they tracked the propagation of Mn²⁺ through axonal tracts and brain regions that are connected to the somatosensory cortex and their results pointed an in vivo deficit in neuronal Mn²⁺ transport in KO MAP6 mice, which might be due to both axonal transport defects and synaptic transmission impairments. They further observed that Epo D treatment eased the axonal transport defects, and this improvement most likely contributed to the positive effect of Epo D on behavioral defects in KO MAP6 mice.

Autism is characterized by abnormal reciprocal social interactions, repetitive behaviors with restricted interests and communication deficits. A quantitative proteomic profiling study demonstrated that STOP / MAP6 protein was significantly reduced in the cerebral cortex from BTBR mouse model of autism compared to the C57BL/6J

mice. Wei et al. [20] showed that the concentration of STOP/MAP6 protein was significantly reduced in the plasma of **autistic** subjects than that in healthy controls. Finally, they proposed a possible mechanism of STOP/MAP6 protein in the pathogenesis of autism.

Autism spectrum disorders (ASD) are neurodevelopmental diseases characterised by deficits in social communication, restricted interests, and repetitive behaviours. Evidence points to a role for cerebellar changes in ASD pathology. Gassowska Dobrowolska et al. [21] generated a rodent model of ASD through a single prenatal administration of valproic acid (VPA) into pregnant rats, followed by cerebellar morphological studies of the offspring, focusing on the alterations of key cytoskeletal elements. They investigated the expression (Western blot) of α/β -tubulin and the major neuronal MT-associated proteins (MAP) like MAP-Tau/1B/2/6(STOP) along with actin-crosslinking α II-spectrin and neurofilament light polypeptide (NF-L). They found that maternal exposure to VPA caused a decrease in the protein levels of α/β -tubulin, MAP-Tau/1B/2, and α II-spectrin. Their immunohistochemical staining showed chromatolysis in the cerebellum of **autistic**-like rats and loss of Purkinje cells, thus shedding light on one of the possible mechanisms that might underlie neuroplasticity alterations in the ASD brain.

The skeletal muscle fiber has a specific and precise intracellular organization which is at the basis of an efficient muscle contraction. Microtubules play a major role in the function and organization of many cells, but in skeletal muscle, the contribution of the microtubule cytoskeleton to the efficiency of contraction has only recently been studied. Sébastien et al. [22] study the role of the MAP6 protein in **skeletal muscle organization and function** using the MAP6 KO mouse line. Based on this they demonstrated the presence of MAP6 transcripts and proteins in skeletal muscle and found that deletion of MAP6 resulted in a large number of muscle modifications like muscle weakness associated with slight muscle atrophy, alterations of microtubule network and sarcoplasmic reticulum organization, and reduction in calcium release. Further, they concluded that as MAP6 KO mouse line was a model for schizophrenia, their results pointed to a possible muscle weakness associated to some forms of schizophrenia.

Osteosarcoma (OS) is the most common type of malignant bone tumor that affects children and adolescents. In their study, Lin et al. [23] identified numerous dysregulated lncRNAs by RNA-seq and found a novel lncRNA Lnc-MAP6-1:3 which was observed to be highly expressed in **osteosarcoma**. Using RT-PCR, gene knockdown, western blotting and oncogenic function assay, they observed that knockdown of Lnc-MAP6-1:3 expression suppressed cell proliferation and colony formation, and promoted apoptosis in vitro. In a first, they identified that Lnc-MAP6-1:3 influenced the malignant behavior of osteosarcoma via Bax/Bcl-2 and Wnt/ β -catenin signaling pathways. Thus they hypothesize that Lnc-MAP6-1:3 might provide a new molecular route of research and therapeutic applications for the diagnosis and treatment of osteosarcoma. Many of the different synergies represented as combinations of genes/proteins have been experimentally tested and published. However, there are combinations that have yet to be explored. I address the problem of identifying these unexplored combinations via use of a machine learning based search engine in the next section.

1.4. Insight behind the work

Across all search engines has the fundamental principle remains the same i.e to capture the pattern available in the data and based on that pattern, rank a list of queries. Different algorithms can be applied, however if the fundamental pattern is captured accurately, then the rankings will remain approximately the same, with slight variations, across the different kinds of search engines used. I use one search engine, however, vary the way the patterns are captured via use of different sensitivity methods. Each sensitivity method uses a different flavour/mathematical formulation to compute the sensitivity indices to estimate the influence of the involved factors. These involved factors are genes that play a role in cell biology, in the above research. The insight is that all methods will capture the sensitivity of the involved factors based on their recorded regulations and the search engine will rank the combination of factors based on these sensitivity indices. Since the role of involved factors are captured properly, the search engine will give appropriate rankings to the combinations, thus capturing which gene combinations might be playing significantly in a biological phenomena. The above work shows rankings for experimentally confirmed combinations as well as unexplored/untested combinations. These rankings are not just numbers. They point to the existence of biological synergy in the form of gene combinations, whether tested in wet lab or unexplored till now. Finally, the findings suggest that the rankings are conserved across the different sensitivity methods used.

1.5. Combinatorial search problem and a possible solution

In a recently published work Sinha [2], a frame work of a search engine was developed which can rank combinations of factors (genes/proteins) in a signaling pathway. The work uses SVM package by Joachims [24] in https://www.cs.cornell.edu/people/tj/svm_light/svm_rank.html. I use the adaptation to rank 2^{nd} order gene combinations. The sensitivity package by Pujol et al. [25] was used to develop the search engine pipeline. The current research uses the Hilbert Schmidt Independence Criterion (HSIC) and SOBOL method, implemented in the sensitivity package mentioned above. I use three different kernels under the HSIC method namely, • laplace, • linear and • rbf. For SOBOL method, I use • sobol-2002, and • sobol-jansen. Each of these variants or kernels have been implemented in the sensitivity package and option has been provided in the search engine code to generate the rankings for a particular gene, using a choice of a kernel/variant at a time. Technical details about the variants and kernels can be found in references citetd in Pujol et al. [25].

2. Methods

2.1. Static data from Patel et al. [1]

Patel et al. [1] analyzed 160 meningioma samples from 140 patients, and according to the WHO histopathological classification system for meningioma, they found 121 tumors were of grade I (benign), 32 were of grade II (atypical), and 7 were of grade III (malignant). To determine whether meningiomas could be differentiated based on

gene expression profiles, they used principal component analysis (PCA) on a discovery set of 97 tumors (i.e 77 WHO grade I and 20 WHO grade II). Next, they employed nonnegative matrix factorization (NMF) clustering (a unsupervised machine-learning approach) for $k = 2$ to $k = 7$ using the 1,500 genes that varied most among the tumor samples. They report that after 1,000 iterations, 3 clusters ($k = 3$) emerged as providing the best fit as determined by the consensus membership, cophenetic, and silhouette scores. They evaluated the cluster significance of the 3 subtypes using SigClust (Huang et al. [26]) and observed statistical significance between cluster boundaries, which exhibited significant differences in WHO grade representation.

2.2. Design for static data from Patel et al. [1]

The procedure begins with the listing of all C_k^n combinations for k number of genes from a total of n genes. Here n can be the choice of the biologist. k is ≥ 2 and $\leq (n - 1)$. Each of the combination of order k represent a unique set of interaction between the involved genetic factors. Since the sensitivity analysis methods require a sample for a particular observation, a steep gaussian distribution was generated with a jitter (noise) added to the deviation from the reported point measurement of 0.005. In this experiment, the distribution contained 10 measurements (including the point of measurement under consideration). This is repeated for each point of measurement.

To have an averaged ranking, the experiment was designed to run for 25 iterations. In each iteration, the datasets are combined in a specified format which go as input as per the requirement of a particular sensitivity analysis method. Thus for each p^{th} combination in C_k^n combinations, the dataset is prepared in a required format. Details of formatting the data have not been presented in the article to maintain the fluidity and brevity. Interested readers can find examples of formating the data in the sensitivity analysis package in R. Sensitivity analysis and its relevance in systems biology have been covered in a recently published article by Sinha [27], which forms the foundation for this work. After the data has been transformed, vectorized programming is employed for density based sensitivity analysis and looping is employed for variance based sensitivity analysis to compute the required sensitivity indices for each of the p combinations.

After the above sensitivity indices have been stored for each of the p^{th} combination, for a chosen sensitivity analysis method, the next step in the design of experiment is conducted. Here, the indices are averaged per combination to have a mean index value. These index values form the discriminative features for a particular combination. For a k^{th} order combination, a vector of k elements or indices forms a feature vector. Thus for C_k^n combinations there will be C_k^n vectors, each containing k elements. Next, SVM_{learn}^{Rank} Joachims [24] is used to generate a model on default value C value of 20. In the current experiment on toy model C value has not been tuned. The training set helps in the generation of the model as the different gene combinations are numbered in order which are used as rank indices. The model is then used to generate score on the observations in the testing set using the $SVM_{classify}^{Rank}$ Joachims [24]. This is followed by sorting of these scores along with the rank indices already assigned to the gene combinations. The end result is a sorted order of the gene combinations based on the ranking score learned by the SVM^{Rank} algorithm.

Note that the following is the order in which the files should be executed in R Team [28], in order, for obtaining the desired results (Note that the code will not be explained here) - • use `source("extractMeningiomadata.R")` • use `source("manuscript-2-2.R")` • use `source("SVMRank-Results-S-mean.R")`.

2.3. Translating the pipeline into code of execution in R

The execution begins by some preprocessing of the file containing the information regarding the down regulated genes via `source("extractMeningiomadata.R")`. The library containing the sensitivity analysis methods is then loaded in the interface using the command `library(sensitivity)` (Note - this package can be downloaded for free from <https://cran.r-project.org/web/packages/sensitivity/index.html>). Next a gaussian distribution for a particular transcript level for a gene is generated to have a sample. This is needed in the computation of sensitivity index for that particular gene. A gene of particular choice is selected (in blue) and the choice of the combination is made (here $k = 2$). Later a kernel is used (here rbf for HSIC method). 25 different indices are generated which help in generating aggregate rank using these 25 indices. The Support vector ranking algorithm is employed to generate the scores for different combinations and these scores are then sorted out. This is done using the command `source("SVMRank - Results - S - mean.R")`. A file is generated that contains the combinations in increasing order of influence. Note that 1 means lowest rank and vice versa, for 2^{nd} order combinations for any gene using a particular density based sensitivity index.

2.4. Regarding biological insight

For the recorded gene expression values, the sensitivity indices are computed. The search engine uses the kernel based density method. The kernel method takes the data, that is in a lower dimensional plane and projects it to a higher dimensional plane, with an idea that in a higher dimensional place, there exists a dot product between the projected data. To simply state, the idea is that in a higher dimensional plane the nonlinearities between the data (in lower dimensional plane) will be captured and the data may be segregated from each other via a hyperplane. So, irrespective of the method used to measure the gene expression values, if the measurements capture biological information (to whatever extent they can), then the kernel method will be able to capture the nonlinearities/synergies, if existing and allow the sensitivity analysis method (here density based method) to estimate the strength of influence of each of the factors. Based on the sensitivity indices of combinations of a particular order, the search engine ranks the combinations. Details of search engine are provided in the published work in Sinha [2].

It is important to note that the search engine will not give insight about the mechanism of synergy between the components of a combination. However, if the synergy exists between components of an unexplored/untested combination, then the sensitivity indices will capture the influence of these components taken together (which form a combination of interest) and will rank the combination appropriately. These rankings

provide insight about which combination a biologist/oncologist might want to test in a forest of combinations for a given scenario in a cell (whether normal or pathological).

3. Results & Discussion

3.1. MAP6 related synergies

Note - MAP6 was found to be upregulated in Type B. Upregulation was defined as Type logFC to be > 1 and $FDR \leq 0.001$, in Patel et al. [1]. Also, sorting of scores by the machine learning algorithm were done in ascending order, i.e - top is lowest in ranking. A total of 392 2nd order combinations of MAP6 were recorded.

3.1.1. MAP6 - individual genes

The following genes in combination with MAP6 showed high rankings - CD38 molecule (CD38), heat shock protein family B (small) member 6 (HSPB6), CD4 molecule (CD4), insulin like growth factor 1 (IGF1), CD74 molecule (CD74), amyloid beta precursor protein binding family A member 2 (APBA2), tetraspanin 32 (TSPAN32), adenylate cyclase 2 (ADCY2), matrix metalloproteinase 2 (MMP2), solute carrier family 23 member 2 (SLC23A2), proprotein convertase subtilisin/kexin type 5 (PCSK5), seizure related 6 homolog like (SEZ6L), nuclear factor of activated T cells 4 (NFATC4), CD40 molecule (CD40), sushi repeat containing protein X-linked (SRPX), procollagen C-endopeptidase enhancer (PCOLCE), contactin associated protein 1 (CNTNAP1), peripheral myelin protein 22 (PMP22), tripartite motif containing 2 (TRIM2), solute carrier family 35 member F2 (SLC35F2), cut like homeobox 2 (CUX2), cadherin 6 (CDH6), par-3 family cell polarity regulator beta (PARD3B), immunoglobulin superfamily member 21 (IGSF21), neuropilin 2 (NRP2), chromosome 1 open reading frame 198 (C1orf198), PHD finger protein 19 (PHF19), PDZ and LIM domain 2 (PDLIM2), C-C motif chemokine receptor 2 (CCR2), PHD finger protein 24 (PHF24), plasminogen activator, urokinase (PLAU), transmembrane protein 35A (TMEM35A), sarcoglycan epsilon (SGCE), microtubule associated protein 1B (MAP1B), matrilin 3 (MATN3), protein tyrosine phosphatase non-receptor type 22 (PTPN22), lymphocyte cytosolic protein 1 (LCP1), cerebellin 3 precursor (CBLN3), fibulin 5 (FBLN5), insulin like growth factor binding protein 4 (IGFBP4), NLR family pyrin domain containing 12 (NLRP12), CTD small phosphatase like (CTDSPL), solute carrier family 2 member 12 (SLC2A12), LanC like family member 3 (LANCL3), carbohydrate sulfotransferase 7 (CHST7), cysteine rich transmembrane BMP regulator 1 (CRIM1), enkurin, TRPC channel interacting protein (ENKUR), VENT homeobox (VENTX), dimethylarginine dimethylaminohydrolase 1 (DDAH1), sushi domain containing 3 (SUSD3), RUNX family transcription factor 1 (RUNX1), matrix remodeling associated 8 (MXRA8), amyloid beta precursor protein binding family B member 2 (APBB2), collagen type I alpha 2 chain (COL1A2), transmembrane protein 71 (TMEM71), HtrA serine peptidase 1 (HTRA1), filamin A interacting protein 1 like (FILIP1L), RAB31, member RAS oncogene family (RAB31), vesicle associated membrane protein 5 (VAMP5), coiled-coil domain containing 126 (CCDC126), secretogranin II (SCG2), interleukin 17D

(IL17D), heart development protein with EGF like domains 1 (HEG1), homeobox B2 (HOXB2), CD248 molecule (CD248), dynein axonemal heavy chain 12 (DNAH12), solute carrier organic anion transporter family member 3A1 (SLCO3A1), myozenin 1 (MYOZ1), cysteine and serine rich nuclear protein 3 (CSRNP3), class II major histocompatibility complex transactivator (CIITA), serine rich and transmembrane domain containing 1 (SERTM1), phospholipase C beta 1 (PLCB1), neurotrimin (NTM), regulator of G protein signaling 6 (RGS6), pappalysin 1 (PAPPA), family with sequence similarity 43 member B (FAM43B), transmembrane protein 119 (TMEM119), olfactomedin like 1 (OLFML1), protein kinase D1 (PRKD1), colony stimulating factor 1 (CSF1), ankyrin repeat domain 20 family member A5, pseudogene (ANKRD20A5P), A-kinase anchoring protein 19 (C2orf88 / AKAP19), kelch repeat and BTB domain containing 12 (KBTBD12), low density lipoprotein receptor class A domain containing 2 (LDLRAD2), ectonucleoside triphosphate diphosphohydrolase 8 (ENTPD8), placenta associated 9 (PLAC9), nuclear GTPase, germinal center associated (NUGGC), family with sequence similarity 180 member A (FAM180A), membrane metalloendopeptidase (MME), family with sequence similarity 180 member B (FAM180B), long intergenic non-protein coding RNA 3124 (C2orf27A / LINC03124), C-type lectin domain containing 9A (CLEC9A), DLG associated protein 2 (DLGAP2), matrix metalloproteinase 17 (MMP17), zinc finger protein 521 (ZNF521), ryanodine receptor 3 (RYR3), ras homolog family member T1 pseudogene 2 (RHOT1P2), phospholipid phosphatase 4 (PLPP4), NALCN channel auxiliary factor 1 (FAM155A / NALF1), transmembrane protein 240 (TMEM240), vitrin (VIT), ankyrin repeat domain 20 family member A9, pseudogene (ANKRD20A9P), glutathione peroxidase 3 (GPX3), high mobility group box 3 pseudogene 7 (HMGB3P7), ankyrin repeat domain 20 family member A11, pseudogene (ANKRD20A11P), teneurin transmembrane protein 3 (TENM3), cytochrome P450 family 4 subfamily F member 29, pseudogene (CYP4F29P), zinc finger protein 883 (ZNF883) and sorting nexin 18 pseudogene 13 (SNX18P13).

Using the adaptation of the above mentioned search engine, I tabulate the rankings of 2nd order combination of MAP6 with the above list, that were reported to be upregulated in Patel et al. [1]. Table 1 and 2 shows rankings of these combinations. Followed by this is the unexplored combinatorial hypotheses in table 3 generated from analysis of the ranks in table 1 and 2.

One can also interpret the results of the table 1 and 2 graphically, with the following influences - ● Individual members w.r.t MAP6 with MAP6 – > CD38 / HSPB6 / CD4 / IGF1 / CD74 / APBA2 / TSPAN32 / ADCY2 / MMP2 / SLC23A2 / PCSK5 / SEZ6L / NFATC4 / CD40 / SRPX / PCOLCE / CNTNAP1 / PMP22 / TRIM2 / SLC35F2 / CUX2 / CDH6 / PARD3B / IGSF21 / NRP2 / C1orf198 / PHF19 / PDLIM2 / CCR2 / PHF24 / PLAU / TMEM35A / SGCE / MAP1B / MATN3 / PTPN22 / LCP1 / CBLN3 / FBLN5 / IGFBP4 / NLRP12 / CTDSPL / SLC2A12 / LANCL3 / CHST7 / CRIM1 / ENKUR / VENTX / DDAH1 / SUSD3 / RUNX1 / MXRA8 / APBB2 / COL1A2 / TMEM71 / HTRA1 / FILIP1L / RAB31 / VAMP5 / CCDC126 / SCG2 / IL17D / HEG1 / HOXB2 / CD248 / DNAH12 / SLCO3A1 / MYOZ1 / CSRNP3 / CIITA / SERTM1 / PLCB1 / NTM / RGS6 / PAPPA / FAM43B / TMEM119 / OLFML1 / PRKD1 / CSF1 / ANKRD20A5P / C2orf88 / KBTBD12 / LDLRAD2 / ENTPD8 / PLAC9 / NUGGC / FAM180A / MME / FAM180B / C2orf27A / CLEC9A / DLGAP2 / MMP17 / ZNF521 / RYR3 / RHOT1P2 / PLPP4 / FAM155A / TMEM240 / VIT / ANKRD20A9P / GPX3

RANKING INDIVIDUAL MEMBERS VS MAP6									
RANKING OF INDIVIDUAL MEMBERS W.R.T MAP6									
	laplace	linear	rbf	jansen		laplace	linear	rbf	jansen
CD38 - MAP6	3	320	322	194	HSPB6 - MAP6	254	248	13	262
CD4 - MAP6	19	330	256	217	IGF1 - MAP6	370	95	191	250
CD74 - MAP6	212	192	279	160	APBA2 - MAP6	237	252	310	238
TSPAN32 - MAP6	130	272	375	191	ADCY2 - MAP6	213	205	167	382
MMP2 - MAP6	269	268	355	93	SLC23A2 - MAP6	248	356	230	121
PCSK5 - MAP6	138	314	203	201	SEZ6L - MAP6	351	136	197	341
NFATC4 - MAP6	256	339	218	136	CD40 - MAP6	292	225	265	144
SRPX - MAP6	385	208	118	290	PCOLCE - MAP6	231	321	247	185
CNTNAP1 - MAP6	205	345	225	173	PMP22 - MAP6	219	255	253	128
TRIM2 - MAP6	386	352	313	110	SLC35F2 - MAP6	215	258	173	388
CUX2 - MAP6	341	190	51	346	CDH6 - MAP6	223	303	221	21
PARD3B - MAP6	227	341	217	359	IGSF21 - MAP6	244	213	323	187
NRP2 - MAP6	157	300	241	213	C1orf198 - MAP6	105	335	302	188
PHF19 - MAP6	313	182	229	116	PDLIM2 - MAP6	281	306	304	86
CCR2 - MAP6	321	102	298	343	PHF24 - MAP6	339	143	258	251
PLAU - MAP6	328	308	122	355	TMEM35A - MAP6	355	254	219	82
SGCE - MAP6	350	302	137	246	MAP1B - MAP6	90	289	184	386
MATN3 - MAP6	349	207	54	295	PTPN22 - MAP6	154	328	272	256
LCP1 - MAP6	378	362	281	182	CBLN3 - MAP6	316	316	319	369
FBLN5 - MAP6	182	312	274	199	IGFBP4 - MAP6	301	244	329	169
NLRP12 - MAP6	66	304	206	221	CTDSPL - MAP6	198	350	285	179
SLC2A12 - MAP6	260	277	213	30	LANCL3 - MAP6	275	193	248	11
CHST7 - MAP6	210	242	308	78	CRIM1 - MAP6	177	376	275	365
ENKUR - MAP6	363	226	262	109	VENTX - MAP6	147	325	239	387
DDAH1 - MAP6	36	282	349	212	SUSD3 - MAP6	25	323	339	193
RUNX1 - MAP6	126	361	251	336	MXRA8 - MAP6	194	290	193	371
APBB2 - MAP6	377	346	196	376	COL1A2 - MAP6	337	294	356	178
TMEM71 - MAP6	221	318	316	203	HTRA1 - MAP6	203	329	205	168

Table 1: 2nd order interaction ranking between MAP6 VS Individual members.

/ HMGB3P7 / ANKRD20A11P / TENM3 / CYP4F29P / ZNF883 / SNX18P13.

4. Conclusion

Presented here are a range of multiple synergistic MAP6 2nd order combinations that were ranked via a machine learning based search engine. Via majority voting across the ranking methods, it was possible to find plausible unexplored synergistic combinations of MAP6-X that might be prevalent in meningioma.

Conflict of interest

There are no conflicts to declare.

RANKING INDIVIDUAL MEMBERS VS MAP6									
RANKING OF INDIVIDUAL MEMBERS W.R.T MAP6									
	laplace	linear	rbf	jansen		laplace	linear	rbf	jansen
FILIP1L - MAP6	242	16	271	206	RAB31 - MAP6	135	292	240	218
VAMP5 - MAP6	272	140	233	379	CCDC126 - MAP6	287	363	284	122
SCG2 - MAP6	71	384	303	291	IL17D - MAP6	103	233	288	381
HEG1 - MAP6	243	235	306	220	HOXB2 - MAP6	5	359	363	373
CD248 - MAP6	190	249	369	68	DNAH12 - MAP6	240	295	341	79
SLCO3A1 - MAP6	92	281	382	245	MYOZ1 - MAP6	241	291	252	76
CSRNP3 - MAP6	299	186	337	195	CIITA - MAP6	191	250	367	108
SERTM1 - MAP6	199	390	389	309	PLCB1 - MAP6	74	342	333	363
NTM - MAP6	273	372	335	288	RGS6 - MAP6	201	373	376	253
PAPPA - MAP6	125	387	373	294	FAM43B - MAP6	217	279	327	391
TMEM119 - MAP6	96	381	254	259	OLFML1 - MAP6	69	203	344	368
PRKD1 - MAP6	107	378	295	296	CSF1 - MAP6	305	305	334	129
ANKRD20A5P - MAP6	128	386	388	302	C2orf88 - MAP6	204	337	320	77
KBTBD12 - MAP6	99	344	280	392	LDLRAD2 - MAP6	164	368	340	276
ENTPD8 - MAP6	193	307	235	27	PLAC9 - MAP6	143	371	384	293
NUGGC - MAP6	6	331	366	372	FAM180A - MAP6	124	377	386	297
MME - MAP6	139	388	385	326	FAM180B - MAP6	64	392	379	301
C2orf27A - MAP6	52	198	311	207	CLEC9A - MAP6	43	332	380	237
DLGAP2 - MAP6	166	336	353	249	MMP17 - MAP6	97	366	364	366
ZNF521 - MAP6	238	340	365	230	RYR3 - MAP6	67	357	314	192
RHOT1P2 - MAP6	169	385	371	334	PLPP4 - MAP6	211	355	381	254
FAM155A - MAP6	300	354	358	90	TMEM240 - MAP6	72	240	347	328
VIT - MAP6	285	389	387	303	ANKRD20A9P - MAP6	222	370	267	317
GPX3 - MAP6	226	382	368	362	HMG3P7 - MAP6	78	365	336	331
ANKRD20A11P - MAP6	257	375	362	282	TENM3 - MAP6	278	380	392	289
CYP4F29P - MAP6	81	383	391	323	ZNF883 - MAP6	55	206	346	345
SNX18P13 - MAP6	159	391	390	333					

Table 2: 2nd order interaction ranking between MAP6 VS Individual members.

Author's contributions

Concept, design, in silico implementation - SS. Analysis and interpretation of results - SS. Manuscript writing - SS. Manuscript revision - SS. Approval of manuscript - SS

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Source of Data

Data used in this research work was released in a publication in Patel et al. [1]. Permission to use, granted by PNAS.

UNEXPLORED COMBINATORIAL HYPOTHESES

Individual members w.r.t MAP6	
CD38 / HSPB6 / CD4 / IGF1 / CD74 ...	
APBA2 / TSPAN32 / ADCY2 / MMP2 ...	
SLC23A2 / PCSK5 / SEZ6L / NFATC4 ...	
CD40 / SRPX / PCOLCE / CNTNAP1 ...	
PMP22 / TRIM2 / SLC35F2 / CUX2 ...	
CDH6 / PARD3B / IGSF21 / NRP2 ...	
C1orf198 / PHF19 / PDLIM2 / CCR2 ...	
PHF24 / PLAU / TMEM35A / SGCE ...	
MAP1B / MATN3 / PTPN22 / LCP1 ...	
CBLN3 / FBLN5 / IGFBP4 / NLRP12 ...	
CTDSPL / SLC2A12 / LANCL3 / CHST7 ...	
CRIM1 / ENKUR / VENTX / DDAH1 ...	
SUSD3 / RUNX1 / MXRA8 / APBB2 ...	
COL1A2 / TMEM71 / HTRA1 / FILIP1L ...	
RAB31 / VAMP5 / CCDC126 / SCG2 ...	
IL17D / HEG1 / HOXB2 / CD248 ...	
DNAH12 / SLCO3A1 / MYOZ1 / CSRNP3 ...	
CIITA / SERTM1 / PLCB1 / NTM ...	
RGS6 / PAPA / FAM43B / TMEM119 ...	
OLFML1 / PRKD1 / CSF1 / ANKRD20A5P ...	
C2orf88 / KBTBD12 / LDLRAD2 / ENTPD8 ...	
PLAC9 / NUGGC / FAM180A / MME ...	
FAM180B / C2orf27A / CLEC9A / DLGAP2 ...	
MMP17 / ZNF521 / RYR3 / RHOT1P2 ...	
PLPP4 / FAM155A / TMEM240 / VIT ...	
ANKRD20A9P / GPX3 / HMGB3P7 / ANKRD20A11P ...	
TENM3 / CYP4F29P / ZNF883 / SNX18P13 ...	MAP6

Table 3: 2nd order combinatorial hypotheses between MAP6 and Individual members.

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